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STATE OF MICROCIRCULATION OF PERIODONTAL TISSUES IN CHILDREN WITH MANDIBULAR FRACTURES

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Relevance. The principle of treatment of mandibular fractures (MF) in children, as well as in adults, consists in the reduction and reliable fixation of bone fragments in the correct position for the entire healing period. The choice of the method of immobilization in the treatment of MF is the most difficult in childhood. In practice, immobilization with the help of Tigestedt's splints (1915) is more often used, although it has a number of disadvantages, the most significant of which are: a negative effect on periodontal tissues, a significant deterioration in the level of oral hygiene and the quality of life of patients [1,2].

Prolonged presence of ligatures in the area of the necks of the teeth can cause the development of an inflammatory process in the periodontal tissues [3,4], and with already existing periodontitis - its exacerbation [5], which significantly complicates the treatment [6,7,8].

Inflammatory processes in the periodontal tissues will inevitably lead to changes in the local circulatory system. Therefore, studying the state of microcirculation of periodontal tissues with MF is an urgent and poorly studied problem.

The above provisions determined the purpose and objectives of this study aimed at studying the state of microcirculation of periodontal tissues in the treatment of MF in children.

Material and methods. We examined the MI (microcirculation index), which represents the result of laser Doppler flowmetry, as well as the diagnostic characteristics of basal blood flow, standard deviation and coefficient of variation. Investigated 26 children aged 3-18 years who received treatment and who were immobilized with Tigerstedt splints in the department Pediatric Maxillofacial Surgery of the clinic of the Tashkent State Dental Institute in the period 2018-2020. and 18 healthy children without dental pathology. The children were divided into 3 groups, depending on their age.

Results. During the analysis of LDFgrams in children with clinically healthy periodontal disease, the following indicators of capillary blood flow were established: the microcirculation indicator was in the group of children 3-5 years old. $12,7 \pm 1,16$ conventional units (c.u.), in children 6-12 years old – $13,23 \pm 1,13$ c.u. and for children 13-18 years old – $11,84 \pm 1,26$ c.u.

When comparing the parameters of microcirculation in the periodontal tissues of children with MF before treatment, with the corresponding parameters obtained in the control, statistically significant changes were revealed. The index of microcirculation decreased in children with MF and was in the age group of 3-5 years $8.8 \pm 1,12$, in the group 6-12 years $9,7 \pm 1,15$ and in children 13-18 years old $7,62 \pm 1,11$. The obtained MI values also indicate a more active microcirculation in children 6-12 years old in comparison with other age groups in healthy children and in children with MF ($p < 0.05$). This is due to the fact that in children of this age group, the process of changing milk teeth with permanent ones is underway and the tissues of the periodontal complex are being reformed. In the course of the study, a deterioration in the indicator of the efficiency of microcirculation in children with MF was recorded in comparison with healthy children by 1,2 times in all age groups.

The indicator of the standard deviation in healthy children, in the age group of 3-5 years was equal to $-1,06 \pm 0,03$ c.u., in children 6-12 years old $-0,94 \pm 0,05$ c.u., in children 13-18 years old $-1,04 \pm 0,06$ c.u. The standard deviation indicator tended to decrease in children with MF and showed the following values: in children 3-5 years old $-0,98 \pm 0,04$, 6-12 years old $-0,78 \pm 0,05$, 13-18 years old $-0,89 \pm 0,06$. Significantly low values were obtained in children 6-12 and 13-18 years old ($p < 0,05$). This parameter, which characterizes the temporal variability of perfusion, indicates a decrease in the values of the average modulation of blood flow in all frequency ranges.

Analysis of the dynamics of periodontal microcirculation indices according to LDF data in children with MF during treatment showed lower indices, since due to an increase in inflammatory processes in the periodontal tissues, microcirculation indices were lower compared to the initial data.

Conclusions.

Thus, the prolonged presence of ligatures in the area of the necks of the teeth and trauma to the papillary and marginal parts of the gums, as well as the unsatisfactory state of oral hygiene in the treatment of MF in children using the traditional method of splinting provoke exacerbation of inflammatory processes in the periodontal tissues and lead to a deterioration in the state of microcirculation and trophism of tissues. The exclusion of traumatism of periodontal tissues during immobilization, as well as a satisfactory state of oral hygiene can contribute not only to reducing treatment complications, but also to reduce the rehabilitation period for patients with MF.

Bibliography:

1. Bragina V.G., Gorbatova L.N. Trauma of the maxillofacial region in children // Human Ecology. 2014. no.2, P.20-24.

2. Supiev T.K., Nurmaganov S.B., Zykeeva S.K. Traumatism of the maxillofacial region in children. Principles of providing emergency medical care // Bulletin of KazNMU. 2015. No. 1. P.100-103.

3. Shomurodov K.E., Kuryazova Z.Kh., Isomov M.M., Fayziev B.R., Mukimov I.I. Improvement of surgical treatment of fractures of the lower wall of the orbit // “Stomatologiya”. 2017. No. 2 (67). P.78-81.

4. Davydova N.V., Firsova I.V., Suetenkov D.E., Oleinikova N.M. Prevention of traumatic injuries of teeth, soft tissues, jaw bones in children and adolescents // Saratov Journal of Medical Scientific Research. 2011. T7. No.1(appendix), P.199-202.

5. Injuries of soft tissues and bones of the face / Ed. Sharogorodsky A.G. GEOTAR-Med. 2004., P.384.

6. Sipkin A.M., Akhtyamova N.E., Akhtyamov D.V. Characteristics of acute traumatic injuries of the maxillofacial region // Russian medical journal. 2016. No.14., P. 932-935.

7. Yakubov R.K., Sharipova A.U., Fayziev B.R., Yakubov R.R., Yakubova N.A. Principles of preoperative preparation, prevention and treatment of early and late postoperative complications in children with jaw fractures // Dentist Kazakhstan. 2008. No. 7. P.116-122.

8. Yakubov R.K., Mukhamedov I.M., Khodzhimetov A.A., Fayziev B.R., Sharipova A.U., Yakubov R.R. Comprehensive diagnosis and treatment of fractures of the lower jaw in children: Methodical recommendations for practical general practitioners, dentists, maxillofacial surgeons, masters. Tashkent. 2009., 15 p.